

CRITERIA FOR DAM SAFETY ASSESSMENT EMPLOYED IN THE BELO MONTE HYDROELECTRIC POWER PLANT

Oscar M. Bandeira^{*}, Daniel T. Leite[†] and João F. A. Silveira[‡]

^{*}Norte Energia S.A.

SCN, Quadra 04 – Bloco B, salas 94 e 1004 – Centro Comercial Varig
CEP 70714-900 - Brasília, Brasil

e-mail: oscarbandeira@norteenergiasa.com.br, webpage: www.norteenergiasa.com.br

Keywords: Safety Assessment, Dam Safety, Risk Assessment, Instrumentation.

Abstract. *Safety assessment of structures has become a constant challenge to mitigate the risks and ensure safety. In Brazil, the entrepreneurs in the hydroelectric sector have been committed to meeting the new demands required by ANEEL Resolution 696/2015, which establishes criteria for dam safety evaluation (PNSB).*

In this article, are presented the criteria for visual field inspection, as well as the instrumentation analysis criteria, used on the 36 dams of Belo Monte HPP to evaluate the effective safety conditions of these structures. The total amount of monitoring instruments in the civil structures of Belo Monte HPP is almost 2.000.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Belo Monte hydroelectric complex has been built on the Xingu River, in the cities of Altamira and Vitória do Xingu, in the State of Pará. When fully built in 2020, it will have a nominal installed capacity of 11,233.1 MW and will be the fourth largest hydroelectric power plant of the world in installed capacity, with twenty-four generating units, of which 06 Bulb-generating units with 233.1 MW in the Pimental site and eighteen Francis units (11,000 MW) in the Belo Monte Site.

The general arrangement of Belo Monte hydroelectric complex, which is a run-of-river power station, is characterized to be one of the largest diversion powerplant in the world, because it presents distinct work sites distant to each other, from the dam structures, with approximately 7 km of extension in the actual stretch of the Xingu River, in the place called Pimental, to the site Belo Monte, where the Main Power House of the project is currently under construction at a distance of approximately 40 km away, in which they are interconnected by the largest Power Canal of the World (For more details, see Ref. [1]), approximately 16 km long and 0.3 km wide, and the Intermediate Reservoir, an artificial reservoir with 27 large dykes, like Dike 13, approximately 2000 m in length, 53 m of height and volume of 5,7 thousand m³, as well as by small dikes, like Dike 1, with 80 m of length, 6 m of height and volume of 5 thousand m³, forming a maximum abrupt drop of 94.12m (See Figure 1).

[†] Norte Energia S.A.

[‡] SBB Engenharia.

Figure 1 – General Arrangement of HPP Belo Monte

Because it is a large hydropower complex, Belo Monte Hydroelectric Plant requires a lot of attention in monitoring the performance of the 36 dams, 01 spillway with 18 spans, 02 powerhouses, 01 large Intake, besides the Power Canal and Graben, which is a complex arenitic geological structure that limits the Intermediate Reservoir.

Below we will briefly discuss visual inspections, instrumentation follow-up, and classification of the safety conditions of Belo Monte HPP structures, which aim to mitigate risks, ensure the safety and resilience of structures.

2 FIELD INSPECTIONS

Monitoring the safety conditions of Belo Monte HPP structures has been a major challenge that Dam Safety Team is facing due to the size of the project. From the beginning of the first filling of the Main Reservoir in November 2015, the field inspection process started, focused on Dam Safety, was initiated by the Norte Energia team, with the support of SBB Engenharia in some cases.

Field inspections are designed to identify anomalies or conditions that may affect dam safety. Thus, it is important to observe all regions of the dam, namely the upstream slope, downstream slope, crest, abutments, reservoir, etc.

Table 2 lists the major anomalies to be observed in structures.

Preferred paths have been defined to be covered so that all relevant regions of the structures are observed, facilitating regular inspections, optimizing time and ensuring their quality. To follow, in Figure 2, the proposed path for regular inspection of Dike 7B, for example, can be observed.

Figure 2 – Proposed Pathway for Regular Inspection of Dike 7B

In order to inspect all the structures of Belo Monte, technicians and engineers had to cover about 100 km, comprising the diverse earth and concrete structures of the sites Belo Monte and Pimental, as well as the Dykes and Power Canal which has 16 km of extension. A drone was used as an important device in the accomplishment and speed up of field inspections.

Since mid-2016, a drone (Phantom Professional Model 3) has been used, which is controlled by Norte Energia technicians, and has provided excellent results, being an important auxiliary tool as an indicator of the movement of rip-rap blocks. The vegetation covering conditions inspections of the downstream slope, regions where drainage works, and slope protections were carried out, according to Figure 3, as well as slope inspections along the Power Canal, according to Figure 4, detecting fissures/cracks, possible slope movements or other anomalies.

Figure 3 - Photo with drone of Dyke 13 in April / 2017

Figure 4 - Power Canal, in a region where cracks were detected

3 INSTRUMENTATION REVIEWS

Through the analysis of the auscultation instruments, the behavior of the structures can be monitored in the reservoir filling and during the period of operation, comparing the measured values with the control values, defined based on the design hypotheses. At Belo Monte Hydroelectric Plant, 1,998 instruments were installed, as follows:

- | | |
|---|------------------------------------|
| • Standpipe Piezometer - PZC807 | • Water Level Meter.....33 |
| • Electric Piezometer- PZF..... 116 | • Inclinator..... 8 |
| • Weir Gauge - MV141 | • Level Reference.....82 |
| • Multiple Extensometer - EMH65 | • Magnetic Recall Meter 12 |
| • Triortogonal Joint Gauges - MTJ77 | • Magnetic Recess Plates 126 |
| • Superficial Mark - MS.....395 | • Atensorial Box.....5 |
| • Thermometer for concrete - TE 141 | • Geodetic Target 11 |
| • Liminimétrica Ruler4 | |

The piezometers installed in the embankment dams of Belo Monte HPP had their control values calculated in design, using mathematical modeling, based on the following criteria:

"Attention" value: Pore-pressure calculated in order to ensure for the downstream slope, the safety factor $FS = 1.50$, as shown in Fig. 5;

Figure 5 – Dyke 7B – Network flow for the establishment of the value of "Attention".

"Alert" value: Pore-pressure calculated in order to ensure for downstream slope, the safety factor $FS = 1,30$; as shown in Fig. 6;

Figure 6 - Dique 7B – Network flow for the establishment of the value of "Attention".

The multiple extensometers, installed in the foundation of the concrete structures, had the control values for the displacements measured by the rods, through mathematical models simulating the application of the dam's own weight and the load due to the hydrostatic pressures of the reservoir, plus uplift pressures. The "Attention" Value was established considering the hardest rock mass, and the "Alert" values considering the mass with deformability modules of the more deformable side (For more details, see Ref. [2]).

For the flowmeters, theoretical evaluations of percolation flows through compacted embankments, plus foundation were performed, but in practice, it was considered more consistent to adopt the following criteria for the specific flow rates per meter of the dam lines, based on experience with the measured flows in some dozens of embankment dams, in Brazil:

"**Attention**" value: Specified flow $Q_{esp} < 2.0 \text{ l / min / ml}$;

"**Alert**" value: Flow rate $2.0 \text{ l / min / ml} < Q_{esp} < 5.0 \text{ l / min / ml}$.

4 CLASSIFICATION OF STRUCTURE SAFETY CONDITION

The lack of knowledge of the safety conditions of the structures, can prevent the necessary measures to be taken for dam safety.

In this sense, Brazilian legislation, through Law 12.334 / 2010 on National Security Policy for Dams and the ANEEL Resolution 696/2015, in which they establish guidelines for the elaboration of the Dams Safety Plan, as well as offer some tools for the classification of safety conditions of the hydroelectric dams in Brazil, allowing the necessary measures for maintenance and resilience to be taken.

Under these assumptions, the Belo Monte HPP structures were classified based on the FSB - Dam Safety Forms, regarding the category of risk and the associated potential damage. All the Belo Monte structures were classified as "B" (Low Risk), but High Potential Damage (see Table 1).

Table 1 - ANEEL - Dam classification matrix

Categoria de Risco	Dano potencial associado		
	Alto	Médio	Baixo
Alto	A	B	B
Médio	B	C	C
Baixo	B	C	C

Thus, the classification of the safety conditions of Belo Monte HPP is based on its Emergency Actions Plan (PAE), in which it presents the possible failure modes for each type of structure, according to Table 2.

Table 2 – Evidence of anomalies associated with failure modes of structures

FAIL MODE	CAUSE	EVIDENCE
GROUND AND ROCK STRUCTURE		
Overtopping	Gates failure and associated electromechanical equipment	· Electromechanical deficiencies found in the test of the floodgates
	Event of exceptional magnitude	· Occurrence of natural events (precipitations and earthquakes) of exceptional magnitude.
Internal erosion by the rock mass or by the foundation or Uncontrolled piping	Internal Drain System Failure	· Water resurgences; · Particles carrying; · Increased poropressions (piezometers readings); · Reduction of flows (flow meters readings); · Subsidy (sinkhole), sinkhole type formed by the drag of the bottom material.
	High hydraulic gradients	· Water resurgences; · Particles carrying; · Increased or reduced poropressions (piezometers readings); · Increase or reduction of flows (flow meters readings); · Subsidy (sinkhole), sinkhole type formed by the drag of the bottom material.
	Concentrated contact/interface flow with concrete structures	· Water resurgences; · Particles carrying; · Elevation of the poropressions (piezometers readings); · Elevation of the flows (flow meters readings); · Differential stresses between earth and concrete structures; · Cracks opening in the contact between structures.
	Percolation paths created by vegetation and / or animals	· Presence of shrub vegetation on the slopes and near the foot of the dam; · Presence of animal burrows.
Global Instability	Low strength of material / foundation	· Mass differential stress; · Cracks and / or erosions appearance; · Subsidence (s); · Critical rupture surface visualization.
Global Instability	Increased poropressions	· Piezometers readings; · Flow meters readings; · Saturation of the mass.
	Seismic events	· Mass differential stress; · Cracks and / or erosions appearances; · Subsidence (s); · Critical rupture surface visualization.

FAIL MODE	CAUSE	EVIDENCE
Local Instability	Fault in slope surface protection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Formation of erosive furrows / ravine through the passage of rainwater; · Failure of surface protection of slopes; · Emergence of cracks and / or erosions; · Rupture surface visualization.
	Surface drainage system failure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Channels obstruction and boxes of passage; · Breakage of rainwater conduction structures.
	Waves in the reservoir and variations in WL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Removal of rip rip blocks; · Sludge from rockfill blocks.
CONCRETE STRUCTURES		
Instability of the structure	Presence or appearance of a preferred sliding plan in the foundation mass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Differential slip between blocks, detected through monitoring; · Surgence of cracks in the concrete or evolution of pre-existing cracks; · Surgence of rupture points in the concrete or worsening of pre-existing ruptures; · Appearance or intensification of water infiltrations in structures; · Misalignment or binding of floodgates.
Instability of the structure	Failure of drainage system or pumping system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Differential slip between blocks, detected through monitoring; · Surgence of cracks in the concrete or evolution of pre-existing cracks; · Surgence of rupture points in the concrete or worsening of pre-existing ruptures; · Appearance or intensification of water infiltrations in structures; · Misalignment or binding of floodgates.
Instability of the structure	Elevation of WL in the reservoir above the WL maximum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Vertical movement of the structure, detected through monitoring; · Surgence of cracks in the concrete or evolution of pre-existing cracks; · Surgence of rupture points in the concrete or worsening of pre-existing ruptures; · Appearance or intensification of water infiltrations in structures;
	Occurrence of combination of loads that favor the tipping of the structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Miss-alignment or binding of floodgates.
Instability of the structure	Seismic events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Appearance of cracks in concrete or sudden evolution of preexisting cracks; · Appearance of rupture points in concrete or sudden worsening of pre-existing ruptures; · Sudden onset or aggravation of infiltration of water into the structures; · Differential sliding between blocks through monitoring; · Misalignment or binding of floodgates.

Ref. [3] - Belo Monte HPP Emergency Action Plan.

After verifying some failure mode and checking the structure's safety factors, the Emergency Levels of the structures are classified, as shown below:

- Level 0 (blue): flood alert for operation of discharge structures
- Level 1 (green): potential dam break situation is developing
- Level 2 (yellow): potential dam break is worsening
- Level 3 (orange): the dam break is imminent
- Level 4 (red): the dam break is occurring or has just occurred.

It should be noted that ANEEL Resolution 696/2015, based on the classification matrix of Electric Energy Enterprises concerning the State of Conservation, defines the following anomalies with a score equal to or greater than 8 (eight), which would be indicative of the development of a potential dam break situation (LEVEL 1)

5 CONCLUSION

Ensuring the Dam Safety is a responsibility of everybody involved in dams construction, because when accidents with dams occur, in addition to human losses, environmental damage, material damage, there is also a moral damage, which reaches the class of " dam builders ", from the hydroelectric sector, from the mining sector or multiple use.

Each year ANEEL, through the Form of Safety of Dams (FSB), updates in its database the safety conditions of each dam, requiring each entrepreneur in the hydropower sector to evaluate the safety conditions of their enterprises, which has denoted an advance in the safety oversight.

However, the monitoring and verification of dam safety conditions should not be limited to legal obligations and mere form filling, but should be part of a safety culture.

It is important to note that in Belo Monte, even small-scale rockfill structures such as Dike 1B, for example, with only 5 m of maximum height and 100 m of length, were well instrumented, in this case with 5 Standpipe Piezometers, 4 surface landmarks and 1 downstream flow meter, totaling 11 instruments and complying with current ICOLD recommendations, in its bulletin No. 157 [4].

Thus we wish that this article can contribute in some way to those involved in dam construction, as a reference tool, for the Dam Safety of other enterprises.

6 REFERENCES

[1] DAM WORLD (2018) – “The Main Challenges of the Power Canal of the Belo Monte Hpp”; Oscar M. Bandeira, Daniel T. Leite, Marcelo B. Boaventura, Marcelo L. Foz, Leandre S. Valino, and Rodrigo J. F. Sarlo, Foz do Iguaçu, PR – Set/2018;

[2] DAM WORLD (2018) – “Dam Foundation Treatment and its Performance at the Belo Monte HPP”; Oscar Bandeira, Raimundo Carvalho, Daniel Leite e João Silveira, Foz do Iguaçu, PR – Set/2018;

[3] Pimenta de Ávila / Engecorps (2015) – PAE – Plano de Ação Emergencial da UHE Belo Monte, Reports with the PAE of the various structures of the Belo Monte HPP.

[4] INTERTECHNE (2012) – “Investigações e Tratamento dos Canalículos na UHE Belo Monte” – Relatório Técnico